

MADRAS

D2.6 Report on the performance of the printed components of the tag

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.6 comprises the description of performance improvement of the printed components of the tag as a result of the materials developed in WP1. It covers the results related to task *T2.1.2 - Printed antennas development*, *T2.1.5 - Multipoint control unit (MCU) design and fabrication*. It also deals also about task *T2.4 - Quality control of the printed materials and devices*.

Regarding Task 2.1.2 and T2.4, the report exposes a summary of the preparation of printed antennas using the selected combination of Ag NP inks. Hence, electrical and mechanical characterization for printed components of demo 1 is presented.

Key performance parameters of the UHF and UWB antenna have been optimized with several full-wave simulations and partially introduced in previous deliverables (D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3). The design of the antennas compatible with UWL reader is simulated to evaluate the effect of electric and dielectric properties of the selected materials on antenna performance. Once the antenna has been designed, key performance parameters are measured in anechoic chamber to avoid any reflection of electromagnetic waves and reproduce free space conditions as in the simulations.

In addition, printed layers and in-mould tags are evaluated in terms of bending as well as the moisture protective effect of the tag assembly in a climate chamber test.

Finally, Task 2.1.5 comprises the development of the Multipoint control unit (MCU) which is being optimized to work at extremely low power.

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List of abbreviations

Ag NW	Silver nanowires
AWCP	Arjowiggings
COC	Centrum organické chemie
D:A	Donor:acceptor
EM	Electromagnetic
ETL	Electron Transport Layer
ETR	eCooltra
EUT	Eurecat
EQE	External Quantum Efficiency
GNK	Genesink
HTL	Hole transport layer
IGZO	Indium gallium zinc oxide
IME	In-mould electronics
INF	InfinityPV
ITO	Indium Tin Oxide
J_d	Dark current
MFC	Microfibrillated cellulose
NC	Nanocellulose
NP	Nanoparticles
OLAE	Organic and large area electronics
OPD	Organic photodetector
PAL	Photoactive layer
PCE	Power conversion efficiency
PI	Polyimide
R_s	Sheet resistance
SMD	Surface mount device
TNG	Tecnopackaging
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
TPU	Thermoplastic Polyurethane
UHF	Ultra-High Frequency
UPA	University of Pardubice
UPS	Ultraviolet Photoelectron Spectroscopy
UWB	Ultra-Wide Band
UWL	Uwinloc
WO ₃ or WO _x	Tungsten oxide
WP	Work package

Introduction

Materials and production process developed in MADRAS project will be validated in two different demonstrators, including a biometric photosensor for user identification and a geotracking flexible tag for the Industry 4.0 sector.

The geotracking tag developed within MADRAS is manufactured in in-mould electronic (IME) framework. IME combines two dissimilar manufacturing processes which are printed electronics and plastic processing such as injection moulding, a commonly used high-volume manufacturing technique.

MADRAS' partner Uwinloc (UWL) has investigated an accurate solution to geolocate assets through Ultra-Wide Band technology without any battery usage. The operation without any battery is possible thanks to far-field wireless power transmission. Then, the main goal within the project is to develop a flexible and low-cost solution.

MADRAS proposed solution will require a less complicated and less expensive manufacturing process. UWL expertise in the field of energy harvesting, has enabled to develop a new miniaturised chip with better sensitivity, within a range more than 30 meters. However, the main constraint in any wireless device is the optimisation of the antenna to efficiently receive or transmit the signal. UWL's solution is based on two antennas:

- Ultra-High Frequency (UHF) used for harvesting the surrounding electromagnetic wave
- Ultra-Wide Band (UWB) frequency at 4 GHz for transmitting the position to a dedicated beacon in the same area.

The important innovation of the flexible geotracking tag developed within MADRAS' is achieved by means of a specific production process. It goes from the choice of the material based on novel conductive inks and nanocellulose foil, the printing process, the hybridisation techniques and the integration through injection moulding.

Finally, the in-mould methodology developed at Eurecat (EUT) is applied over the antennas and control unit assembly. Substrate and inject moulded material should be appropriately chosen to both have interesting radiofrequency transparency and be flexible.

Purpose of the document

This document presents the advances related to *T2.1.2 Printed antennas development*, *T2.1.5 Multipoint control unit (MCU) design and fabrication*. and *T2.4 Quality control of the printed materials and devices* conducted for development and validation of the performance of Demo 1 printed components.

The objectives reflected in the deliverable are the following:

- Electrical and dielectric characterization of selected conductive ink, substrate, and injected thermoplastic for development of antennas
- Quality control by means of bending test and climate chamber experiments.
- Electrical and mechanical characterization of in-mould antennas with selected materials.
- Multipoint control unit development.

1. Characterization of selected materials for antenna development

1.1 Electrical and dielectric characterization

1.1.1 Electrical characterization of Ag nanoparticles layers

Genesink (GNK) has reported in deliverables D1.1 and D1.4 the development of two different Ag NP-based inks: one with the highest conductivity compatible with paper-based substrate (S-CS91349) and second with enhanced adhesion properties onto PET and CNF-based substrates (S-CS91367) but in detriment to the ink conductivity which could impact the RF performance of the antennas. Their electrical performances are summarized in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** Summary of the electrical performance of the Ink S-CS91349 and S-CS91367.

Table 1. Summary of the electrical performance of the Ink S-CS91349 and S-CS91367.

Ink code	Ink name	Properties	Rs (mops)	Thickness (µm)	Resistivity (µOhm.cm)	Adhesion properties
S-CS91349	Smart Screen B	Highly conductive	22 ± 8	2.3 ± 0.3	4.8 ± 0.8	Bad adhesion to grade 1 NCF / 4B adhesion to PU coated NCF
S-CS91367	Smart Screen A	With additive based on vinyl acrylic copolymer	130 ± 30	1.7 ± 0.3	20 ± 1	5B adhesion on Grade 1 NCF, decreased conductivity 5B adhesion to PU coated NCF

Smart Screen B (Highly conductive ink) was the final choice for development of demos because, although it has bad adhesion to grade 1 CNF, it shows 4B adhesion to PU-coated CNF, the final chosen substrate. Different curing procedures were explored for sintering of Ag NP layers and are exposed below.

Sintering of Ag NP layers on PU-coated substrates: Photonic curing

As explained in deliverable D2.4, sintering of Ag NP on 1st batch of PU-coated substrates was difficult and additional photonic curing was found as a solution to achieve proper sintering. Photonic curing could not be further explored as the equipment at EUT was broken down.

Sintering of Ag NP layers on PU-coated substrates: Oven curing

Screen printing of Smart Screen A and B was tested on the selected substrate for tags, the PU-coated CNF grade 1. AWCP obtained the following good results with oven curing:

ink	Average resistance (@ 6' 110°C) mΩ/□	SD	Average resistance (@ 10' 120°C) mΩ/□	SD	Average resistance (@5' 140°C) mΩ/□	SD
Smart Screen A	687	170	232	46	139	19
Smart Screen B	144	27	97	12	69	8

Table 2. Electrical resistance of PU coated samples printed with Smart Screen A and B.

At EUT, lower sheet resistance of 23-35 mΩ/sq could be obtained for Smart Screen B layer by applying a precuring at 110°C for 10 minutes plus a 140°C treatment for 15 minutes at a reflow oven with top and bottom hot air heating.

Sintering of Ag NP layers on PU-coated substrates: NIR laser sintering

Moreover, the Ag layers on the CNF-based substrates were treated by NIR laser sintering at UPA using a 1064 nm laser. The laser power (20 W) was set at 22% power, the laser frequency was 100 KHz, the scanning beam speed was 2000 mm/s at the line spacing 50 μm. Laser sintering reduced the sheet resistance by approximately 3 times as shown in Table 1.

Printing passes	Ink code	Ink name	Rs (mops)	Rs (mops) Laser sintered
1	S-CS91349	Smart Screen B	131 ± 5	47 ± 3
2	S-CS91349	Smart Screen B	110 ± 3	33 ± 1

Table 3. Summary of the electrical performance of the Ag layers sintered by NIR laser.

1.1.2 Dielectric characterization of TPU

In order to harvest enough surrounding energy for the location tag, an omnidirectional UHF antenna with high radiation efficiency is required. As observed in deliverable D2.2, the dielectric parameter of the substrate and surrounding environment (permittivity and losses), depending on the frequency, greatly affect the impedance and the radiation efficiency of the antenna.

The TPU grade to be used for the injection moulding should be chosen to meet the specifications for radio-frequency (RF) transparency. Its dielectric loss (>1) can be useful for miniaturizing antennas but can also reduce its radiation efficiency. The dissipation factor or loss tangent of the TPU must be as low as possible for higher radiation efficiency, thus for a competitive geotracking tag.

Figure 1. Resonator methods used for TPU characterization: (a) Quarterwavelength stub line resonator, (b) Microstrip ring resonator

EUT has selected two TPU grade: Standard TPU 15N80 and Eco-friendly TPU D12T80E TPU(ECO). Microstrip lines were screen printed on top of injected samples with both TPU to characterize their dielectric properties. The resonator was printed with UV curable standard silver ink (ELG-410S fro Norcode) on 7cmx7cmx1.25mm samples. The method of extracting the dielectric properties consists of printing a microstrip resonator (quarter-wavelength stub line and ring resonator) and measuring the transmission coefficient (S_{21} or S_{12}). The design and the measured samples are presented below (Figure 1).

Two samples of standard TPU 15N80 grade and one of the TPU ECO were measured. The $|S_{21}|$ or $|S_{12}|$ response of the resonators are shown in Figure 2. The calculation of the dielectric constant (D_k) gives an approximate value depicted in Table 2 and Table 3. Both TPU grade have a ϵ_r about 3.3 (± 0.12). This value will be used for next simulation of antennas with TPU in order to have their resonance frequency at 868 MHz according to the specification.

The extraction of the loss tangent which depends on the radiation losses (negligible in some cases) and the conductor loss, is more critical and requires complex calculations.

Figure 2. Measured transmission coefficient using : (a) The stub line resonator, (b) the ring resonator.

Table 4. Measured resonance frequency and extracted dielectric constant for each TPU grade with the stub line method.

N	TPU D12T80E			TPU 15N80 (1)			TPU 15N80 (2)		
	1	3	5	1	3	5	1	3	5
Freq (GHz)	1.05	3.22	5.42	1.03	3.22	5.35	1.04	3.22	5.41
ϵ_{eff}	2.63	2.53	2.48	2.75	2.53	2.55	2.7	2.53	2.49
ϵ_r	3.4	3.25	3.18	3.57	3.25	3.28	3.5	3.25	3.19

Table 5. Measured resonance frequency and extracted dielectric constant for each TPU grade with the ring resonator method.

N	TPU D12T80E			TPU 15N80 (1)			TPU 15N80 (2)		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Freq (GHz)	2.01	4.07	6.06	1.99	4.07	6.05	2	4.07	6.05
ϵ_{eff}	2.57	2.51	2.55	2.63	2.51	2.56	2.60	2.51	2.56
ϵ_r	3.31	3.22	3.28	3.39	3.22	3.29	3.35	3.22	3.29

1.2 Mechanical characterization of Ag NP layer on CNF and on in-mould stack

Behaviour of the conductivity of Ag NP lines printed on CNF and on in-mould assembly under cyclic strain has been tested. The evaluated ink was the one with improved adhesion (IA, Smart Screen A).

The method used to determine the variation of resistance of Ag NP/CNF and TPU/Ag NP/CNF stacks upon bending cycles consisted in characterizing a printed and in-mould conducting stripe of 12 x 73 cm upon 400 bending cycles. As shown in Figure 3-left, the stripe was fabricated at EUT with two side overhanging to allow contacting, for instance, with crocodile clips. UPA conducted the mechanical characterization. The experimental set up consisted in a x-y moving stage where its linear movement was programmed by G-code. The samples were attached into 3D printed clamps and fastened by screws. Then, they were contacted by crocodile contacts. For the measurement of resistance, the acquisition station Keithley DAQ6510 was used with acquisition time cca 43 ms. As depicted in Figure 4, bending tests for all samples orientations were proven: TPU/print top/down. The obtained resistances of samples were plotted in form R/R_0 .

Figure 3 - Scheme of orientation of samples within bending test, image of samples of TPU/Ag NP/CNF stack, detail of bending test experimental set-up.

Figure 4 - Bending orientation (top/down) for the two sample configurations: printed Ag NP/CNF stack (print) and in-mould TPU/Ag NP/MFC stack (TPU).

Several samples described in Table printed on different substrates (grade 1, 1-side PVDC coated CNF foil) and different number of layers (1, 2 and 3) were tested various combination of prints and materials which could be seen in Table 6.

Sample	Test chart. Line size	NCF substrate	Ink	# layers	R _p (Ω)	TPU injected
25	70 × 13 mm	Grade 1	IA	3	5.6	no
16	70 × 12 mm	1-pvdc	IA	2	2.64	no
23	70 × 12 mm	1-pvdc	IA	1	3.7	no
24	70 × 12 mm	1-pvdc	IA	1	3.7	yes
26	70 × 12 mm	1-pvdc	IA	3	3.8	yes

Table 6. Description of samples for bending test of various TPU/Ag NP/CNF and Ag NP/CNF stacks.

Figure 5. R/R_0 data for bending tests for TPU/Ag NP/CNF stacks (TPU) in top/down bending orientations.

Figure 6. R/R_0 data for bending tests for Ag NP/CNF stacks (print) top/down bending orientations.

As shown in Figure 5, results regarding in-mould stacks revealed a measurable resistance change within each bending cycle, which could be better observed in Figure 5-inset. The resistance change is higher for orientation TPU down, where the Ag NP layer is more stretched. On the other side, after ending of the bending cycle the resistance is going back to its starting level. This fact is proven in all the samples, with no trend in R/R_0 within 400 cycles. Besides, from inspected data it seems that samples with only 1 layer (s24) have a lower change of resistance within a bending cycle than samples with 3 layers (s26) of Ag NP.

Regarding samples without in-mould layer, Ag NP/CNF (print), no trend in resistance change within bending test is observed as well. As observed in Figure 6, there is much lower change of resistance within cycle in comparison to TPU-injected samples in Figure 5, as there is no additional stretching stress from injected layer. Overall it could be concluded, that all tested combinations of stacks at a bending radius of 15 mm survived and that there is no obvious trend in resistance change. From test is clear that TPU/Ag NP/CNF assembly resist up to 400 bending cycles, with resistance variations upon each bending cycle of less than 3 % for the worse case.

1.3 Characterization of moisture protective effect of the in-mould stack

To test the moisture protective effect of the hermetical encapsulation provided by the in-mould layer, selected in-mould assemblies were exposed to humidity (up to 90%) and temperature (up to 50°C) in a climate chamber.

Same samples used for bending test were prepared for these experiments as a first approximation: a printed stripe with two side overhanging to allow contacting.

Samples under test were printed on grade 1 (without protective layer) and 1-side PVDC coated CNF (PVDC layer coated on the outside) and injected with TPU. As observed in Figure 7, samples did not withstand testing conditions and peeled off from TPU after exposure.

Figure 7. Images of the sample after climate chamber experiment (exposed 24 to 90% Rh and 50°C). Image on the left show how CNF foil peel off from TPU.

In view of this results, encapsulation and adhesion improvement were discussed between AWCP and EUT. Some coating strategies were proposed:

- 1) PU coating on CNF foils: to improve TPU adhesion.
- 2) Coating CNF foils with different degrees of PVDC: to improve the adhesion of PVDC to nanocellulose.
- 3) In a second step, PU coating in one side and PVDC on both sides or the outside: to have increased adhesion and add protection to moisture.

As presented in deliverable D2.4, the strategy that resulted in the best adhesion to injected TPU was the application of PU-coating on CNF foils. The PU emulsion used for coating of the CNF has a cross-linker that helps to resist temperature and humidity. The chosen TPU for final tag was ESTANE® 58125 NAT 055, a pure ether grade of TPU with enhanced resistance to hydrolysis. Stability of the injected tags after exposure to 90%RH and 50°C for 300 h was tested in a climate chamber. As shown in Figure 8 samples did not show any apparent degradation and CNF foil remained fully adhered. This experiment will be repeated with functional units to check functionality of the tags after exposure to harsh environmental conditions.

Figure 8. CNF-based and PET-based tags before and after climate chamber test.

2. UHF and UWB antennas development

The final demo 1 of the geotracking tag may have two antennas, one for the lower frequency (UHF) to harvest the EM (electromagnetic) waves and the UWB one to transmit the location position. The development of these antenna starts with the simulation on EM software considering the parameters (dielectric and thickness) of each material (NCF foil, Ag Ink and TPU).

The first simulations before prototyping were performed using an arbitrary dielectric constant of the TPU (4.5) found on the literature. The UHF antenna was optimized to have it resonance frequency at 868 MHz with a 1.25 mm Thick TPU as presented in Figure 9. After retrosimulation with the measured value of the TPU dielectric constant (3.3), the UHF antenna present a resonance frequency around 900 MHz for both Ag NP based ink. HC (High conductivity) and IA (Improved adhesion) for CS91349 and CS91367, respectively.

Figure 9. (a) Design of the UHF antenna, (b) Simulated return loss (S_{11}) for both Ag NP based ink with a TPU of 1.25mm thick and dielectric constant (ϵ_r) at 3.3.

2.1 Electrical characterization of in-mould antennas

Comparison of performance of both inks has been evaluated in injected samples. The samples with TPU were characterized in anechoic chamber to avoid the influence of surrounding object. Additionally, they were attached to a rohacell material to facilitate measurement in flat condition of the substrate (rohacell has a dielectric permittivity close to that of air).

Figure 10. Measured antenna under test (connected to RF cable through a UFL-SMA adapter).

As seen below, the measured S_{11} (dB) is modified by the TPU. For thicker TPU (2.5mm), the resonant frequency of the antenna (at 50 Ω) decreases. The use of injected antenna on TPU is interesting for miniaturization because of the guided wavelength modified by its dielectric permittivity. However, it also includes loss and trends to reduce the radiation efficiency of the antenna. The resistivity of the ink also affects the magnitude of the return loss what was not observed during simulation (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Comparison of the measured antennas with high conductivity (CS91349) and improved adhesion (CS91367): UHF (Left) and UWB (Right). Samples with improved adhesion in red line and those with high conductivity in blue line.

2.2 Characterization of bending effect on in-mould antennas

In-mould antennas were measured under two bending radius conditions in the vertical and horizontal plane with an adjustable nylon clamp as seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Antenna to test under bending conditions : (a) Horizontal plane , (b) Vertical plane, (c) Radius definition.

Figure 13. Measured return loss (S11) of the UHF (left) and UWB (right) with different bending radius and orientation plane.

The variation of return loss is more significant for UHF antenna (narrow band), when regarding the matching at 50Ω through the return loss (S_{11}). In both plane, the resonant frequency tends to be shifted at higher frequency (around 920 MHz) but in horizontal the magnitude of the return loss increases and unlike to the vertical plane. UWB antennas stay still matched with $S_{11} \leq 10$ dBm.

3. Multipoint control unit development

The geo-tracking flexible tag combines UHF and UWB antennas to be connected to UWL' electronic module (MCU). The MCU embed the harvester chip (for UHF), the microcontroller and the transmission unit (for UWB).

Figure 14. Block diagram of the Uwinloc tag

The previous version of the MCU was optimized to extremely low power. This MCU that are currently under development will lower the energy needed to an estimated 5 - 10 μ J, achieving the -29 dBm range. Practically, UWL believe -27 dBm to be readily achievable, resulting in a TAG-to-source distance of up to 30 meters. Moreover, with the appropriate technology, the capacitor voltage can be lowered bringing even more gain by reducing the power leakage. The harvester efficiency achieves 33%, delivering 1.3 μ W.

Figure 15. Electronic module to be hybridized for the final demo (Left) and representation of the impedance connection of the antenna.

This module features two differential input pads for the antennas. The characterization of preliminary antennas at 50Ω impedance is necessary to have enough information about the materials before designing them on complex conjugate.

The complex conjugate matching impedance technique is used to avoid matching network through the insertion loss of lumped components. The requirement is to design an antenna with the same real part ($R_a=R_m$) and opposite imaginary part ($X_a=-X_m$) of the MCU impedance. Its final position on the foil is not yet determined as it depends on the design of the antennas to optimise performance.

For UWB part, its impedance is measured with RF probes as seen in Figure 16. The antenna will be designed at an impedance around $Z= 26 + j*10.5$ at 4 GHz.

Figure 16. MCU under test for impedance measurement (Left) and Measurement of the UWB input impedance.

For the UHF part, the input impedance is capacitive with a real part representing the absorption of power. Both real and imaginary part are function of the input power from the antenna.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The first simulations of prototypes were performed using conducting properties of Ag NP inks and arbitrary dielectric constant of the TPU found on the literature. The UHF antenna was optimized to have its resonance frequency at 868 MHz with a 1.25 mm thick TPU as superstrate. In this document, we report electrical and dielectric characterization of selected conductive ink and injected thermoplastic for development of antennas. Electrical properties of developed Ag NP inks, on named Highly conductive (HC) and with Improved adhesion (IA) are summarized.

For the final demo the selected materials have been PU-coated CNF substrates; highly conductive ink (Smart Screen B) and TPU ESTANE® 58125 NAT 055, a pure ether grade of TPU with enhanced resistance to hydrolysis. Also, the PU emulsion used for coating of the CNF has a cross-linker that helps to resist temperature and humidity. HC ink was the final choice for development of demos because, although it has bad adhesion to grade 1 CNF, it shows 4B adhesion to PU-coated CNF. Different curing procedures were explored for sintering of Ag N: oven curing, photonic and NIR laser sintering.

Moreover, a method of extracting the dielectric properties of injected thermoplastic is presented. The precise characterization of dielectric parameters will allow to the best accuracy in simulations for the complex conjugate design for demo.

After retrosimulation with the measured value of TPU dielectric constant (3.3), the UHF antenna resonance frequency was shifted towards 900 MHz for both Ag NP based ink (HC and IC). Then, comparison of performance of both inks on injected samples showed that the resistivity of the ink can affect the magnitude of the return loss what was not observed during simulation.

Climate chamber experiments revealed that tags done with selected PU-coated CNF substrate resist 300h at 50°C and 90%RH without any apparent degradation as loss of adherence or cracking of CNF foil.

Besides, mechanical properties of the assembly are evaluated. Bending tests realized for TPU/Ag NP/CNF and Ag NP/CNF stacks demonstrated that Ag NP layers are mechanically stable upon 400 bending cycles. The resistance change for all samples is less than 3% for each bending cycle. For the overall experiment, resistance was stable and without any trend.

For antennas, bending tests are also performed proving that the impedance of the antenna will be changed depending on the bending plane and radius. The next design will be optimized not to have the exactly targeted impedance or return loss in flat condition but to have the best trade-off between the different bending scenarios.

Finally, a Multipoint control unit (MCU) optimized to work at extremely low power has been developed.

5. Risk analysis

The table presented below describes the potential risk and deviations during the project and the contingency plan that would minimize the risk related to the deliverable D2.6.

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
Ag NW ink doesn't achieve the expected conductivity and transparency	Medium	Mixture of NW with NPs, curing by different techniques or tuning the thickness of the coating	GNK/Ag NPs based inks were developed for antennas applications (higher conductivity), Ag NW ink coating has been optimized to get the better compromised between transparency and conductivity
Printed antennas do not show expected impedance / conductivity	Low	Print with alternative nanoparticles inks prepared within the consortium. Use advanced sintering techniques such as photonic and NIR laser curing.	Mitigate since beginning of the project
Crumpling of the nanocellulose foil during processing, or sensitivity to operational temperature	Medium	Change the solvent of the inks, use laser etching, and alternative curing methods. Work under 150°C	Not detected
Low compatibility between the injection moulding material and the printed device	High	Use of rough (less transparent) NCF for application in Demo 1	The final solution found has been to add a PU coating on NCF which has good adhesion both to NCF and to injected TPU. Use of rough NCF and μ -embossing strategies were tested but it did not result in an increase of adhesion.
Reproducibility of the SMD process	Medium	Redesign of the foil, reallocate the components in the optoelectronics -identify the worse scenario and check that the process is still embedding the components.	Nothing to report
In-mould antenna does not achieve enough water moisture resistance	Medium	1. Use a protective coating on exposed side of NCF substrate. 2. Test different grade PVDC, that require different thermal conditions and possess different water moisture resistance;	EUT/ Search for thermoplastics with water moisture resistance. ARJO/ Fabrication of CNF with 1 side protective

Risk description	Likelihood	Contingency plan	Who/Actions
		3. Use an injected thermoplastic with low OTR and VWTR; 4. Use a moisture resistant adhesive to NCF. "	coating layers as PVDC is ongoing Update: The final stack uses PU-coated CNF foils and TPU. PU emulsion used for coating of the CNF has a cross-linker that helps to resist temperature and humidity. The chosen TPU for final tag was ESTANE® 58125 NAT 055, a pure ether grade of TPU with enhanced resistance to hydrolysis.
Delays in delivery of assets (all)	Low	Day to day coordination of the activities to prevent it	Nothing to report
Unforeseen conflict between partners (IPR issues, etc) or defaulting party (all)	Low	Build professional working relationships, Signature of Consortium Agreement beforehand, with provision of legal basis for conflict resolutions or/and defaulting mechanisms.	Nothing to report

Table 7. Risk Analysis.